

New records of weevils (Coleoptera, Curculionidae) from Western Siberia

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Abstract

There are the westernmost records of *Dorytomus penecke* and *Catapionus quadrilineatus*, and the first record of *Cardipennis rubripes* from Novosibirsk Oblast. Distribution maps for these species are given.

Keywords

Curculionoidea, weevils, fauna, new findings, Siberia

Introduction

The family Curculionidae is one of the diverse groups of Coleoptera. Data on the fauna of Western Siberia were summarized in the review (Legalov 2010) and are presented in regional lists (Krivets 1997; Legalov and Opanassenko 2000; Krivets and Legalov 2002; Bukhkalov et al. 2011; Filimonov 2012). New materials are collected every year. There are new records. This work provides data on the distribution of three species. The first record in the east of Western Siberia for cannabis pest *Cardipennis rubripes* (Hustache, 1916) is presented. The genus *Catapionus* Schoenherr, 1842 is an Asian mountain genus (Alonso-Zarazaga and Lyal 1999), but one species lives to the southeast of the West Siberian Plain. *Dorytomus penecke* Zumpt, 1933 is distributed in Siberia and the Far East. For these species, the most western records are given.

Material and methods

Specimens of new records are kept in CSRN – the private collection of S.V. Reshetnikov (Novosibirsk), and additional material in the Institute of Systematics and Ecology of Animals of the Siberian Branch, Russian Academy of Sciences (Novosibirsk) and Zoological Institute, Russian Academy of Sciences (Saint-Petersburg).

The photographs were taken with a camera Fujifilm X-T10.

The systematics of studied taxa are from the Legalov's works (Legalov 2018, 2020a, 2020b).

Results

Superfamily Curculionoidea Latreille, 1802

Family Curculionidae Latreille, 1802

Subfamily Eriirhininae Schoenherr, 1825

Subtribe Dorytomini Bedel, 1886

Genus *Dorytomus* Germar, 1817

Dorytomus penecke Zumpt, 1933

Fig. 1a

Material examined. 1 female (CSRN), Novosibirsk Oblast, Toguchinskii Distr., 7 km S of Koltyrak, near Mokrushino, *Populus tremulae*, 10.X.2017, S. Reshetnikov.

Remarks. This beetle was collected from very rotten aspen wood lying on the ground. The species develops on *Populus tremulae* L. (Egorov et al. 1996).

Distribution. *Dorytomus penecke* is North Asian species known from South Siberia, Mongolia, Northeast China and the Russian Far East (Fig. 2). This is the westernmost record.

Subfamily Conoderinae Schoenherr, 1833

Supertribe Ceutorhynchitae Gistel, 1848

Tribe Ceutorhynchini Gistel, 1848

Genus *Cardipennis* Korotyaev, 1980

Cardipennis rubripes (Hustache, 1916)

Figs 1b, c

Material examined. 1 ex. (CSRN), Novosibirsk Oblast, Salair Ridge, border of Toguchinskii and Maslyaninskii Districts, valley of Suenga River, 10.VI.2018, S. Reshetnikov.

Remarks. The species develops on *Cannabis sativa* L. (Shilenkov and Tolstonogova 2006).

Figure 1. Representatives of Curculionidae: **a** *Dorytomus peneckeii*, female; **b** *Cardipennis rubripes*, dorsally; **c** *C. rubripes*, laterally; **d** *Catapionus quadrilineatus*, male, dorsally; **e** *C. quadrilineatus*, female, dorsally

Figure 2. Distribution of *Dorytomus peneckeii* in Russia.

Figure 3. Distribution of *Cardipennis rubripes*.

Figure 4. Distribution of *Catapionus quadrilineatus*.

Distribution. This species was known from South Siberia, North Mongolia and the south of Primorskii Krai (Fig. 3). It was also collected in the Chelyabinsk Oblast (Filimonov 2012). This is the first record from Novosibirsk Oblast.

Subfamily Entiminae Schoenherr, 1823

Supertribe Polydrusitae Schoenherr, 1823

Tribe Cneorhinini Lacordaire, 1863

Genus *Catapionus* Schoenherr, 1842

***Catapionus quadrilineatus* (Gebler, 1829)**

Figs 1d, e

Material examined. 1 male (CSRN), 1 female (CSRN), Novosibirsk Oblast, Chulymskii Distr., Bolshedorozhnoe, 55°06'31.9"N, 81°13'26.4"E, in copula, 4.VI.2017, S. Reshetnikov.

Distribution. This species is distributed from the south-east of Western Siberia, Eastern Kazakhstan and the mountains of Central Asia (Fig. 4). It is the westernmost record of this species.

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References

- Alonso-Zarazaga MA, Lyal CHC (1999) A world catalogue of families and genera Curculionoidea (Insecta: Coleoptera) (excepting Scolytidae and Platypodidae). Entomopraxis, Barcelona, 315.
- Bukhhalo SP, Galich DE, Sergeeva EV, Alemasova NV (2011) Synopsis of beetle fauna of the southern taiga of Western Siberia (lower of Irtysh basin). KMK, Moscow, 267. [In Russian]
- Egorov AB, Zherichin VV, Korotyaev BA (1996) Fam. Curculionidae – dolgonosiki ili sloniki. A key to Insects of the Russian Far East. Vladivostok 3 (3), 249–311, 431–516. [In Russian]
- Filimonov RV (2012) Toward fauna of weevils (Coleoptera, Curculionoidea) of the natural reserve «Chernyi Bor» (Chelyabinsk region). Proceedings of the Orenburg branch of the Russian Entomological Society 2, 77–94. [In Russian]
- Krivets SA (1997) A review of the weevil fauna (Coleoptera: Brentidae, Dryophthoridae, Curculionidae) of Tomsk Province. Proceedings of the Russian Entomological Society. St. Petersburg 78 (1), 48–83. [In Russian]

- Krivets SA, Legalov AA (2002) A review of the superfamily Curculionoidea (Coleoptera) fauna of Kemerovo province. Entomological Review 82 (7), 816–831.
- Legalov AA (2010a) Annotated checklist of species of superfamily Curculionoidea (Coleoptera) from Asian part of the Russia. Amurskii Zoologicheskii Zhurnal 2 (2), 93–132.
- Legalov AA (2018) Annotated key to weevils of the world. Part 3. Subfamily Conoderinae (Coleoptera, Curculionidae). Ukrainian Journal of Ecology 8 (4), 494–503.
- Legalov AA (2020a) Annotated key to weevils of the world. Part 4. Subfamilies Eriirhininae, Dryophthorinae and Cossoninae (Curculionidae). Ukrainian Journal of Ecology 10 (2), 319–331. https://doi.org/10.15421/2020_104
- Legalov AA (2020b) Annotated key to weevils of the world. Part 5. Subfamily Entiminae (Curculionidae). Ukrainian Journal of Ecology 10 (2), 332–346. https://doi.org/10.15421/2020_105
- Legalov AA, Opanassenko FI (2000) A review of the fauna of the superfamily Curculionoidea (Coleoptera) of Novosibirsk province. Entomological Review 80 (3), 282–303.
- Shilenkov VG, Tolstonogova EV (2006) Phytophagous insects on *Cannabis* in Baikal Region. Bulletin of the East Siberian Scientific Center of the Siberian Branch of the Russian Academy of Medical Sciences 2 (48), 159–160. [In Russian]